

Constraints to Utilization of HIV/Aids Prevention Strategies among Rural Women in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined constraints to utilization of some selected HIV/AIDS prevention strategies, with a view to measuring it and making recommendations there from as way to mitigate the spread of the epidemic. A multistage sampling procedure was used for selecting 180 respondents for the study. Interview schedule was designed to obtain information from the respondents. The statistical analytical tools employed for the study included both descriptive (frequencies counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and the inferential statistical tools such as Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used. The major findings of the study show that majority of the respondents were more than 30years of age, while the mean age of the respondents was 34.8years. Many (60.6%) of the respondents were married, large population of the respondents were literate with mean year of schooling of 9.59. The distribution of the respondents by their information needs revealed that information on finance ranked first with WMS of 2.76 while health ranked second with the WMS of 2.38. Interaction with health worker, market and radio were the major sources through which information on the HIV/AIDS preventive strategies was gotten by the respondents. Majority (85%) of the respondents indicated avoiding sharing of sharp objects and condom use (84.4%) as the major HIV/AIDS preventive strategies that the respondents were aware of. Fidelity, (2.09) and Avoiding sharing of sharp objects (1.59) were the major preventive strategies the respondents had more knowledge about. Avoidance of sharing of sharp objects (1.76) and condom use (1.63) ranked first and second respectively as the major preventive strategies commonly used by the respondents, stigmatization and unavailability of the preventive strategies were the major constraints to the use HIV/AIDS preventive strategies.

*The results of Pearson Product Moment Correlation showed a significant relationship between some selected socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and the utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies revealed that a significant relationship exists between age ($r = 0.219^{**}$, $p = 0.003$) of the respondents, years of schooling ($r = 0.606^{**}$, $p = 0.000$) and the years of staying in the community ($r = 0.326^{**}$, $p = 0.000$) and utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies. Since stigmatization was reported to be the major constraint to the utilization of the preventive strategies, it's therefore recommended that more awareness needs to be done against stigmatization of the usage of various preventive strategies and Condom should be made readily available to the respondents in order to curb the menace of HIV/AIDS.*

Keywords: Prevention strategies, Rural Women, HIV/AIDS, Constraints

Introduction

Rural women have many roles, and they have responsibilities and knowledge that differ from those of men. As farmers, they plant, weed and harvest food crops and tend livestock. As caretakers, they look after children and relatives, prepare meals and manage the home. Many women earn extra income by working as wage labourers, producing and selling vegetables, or engaging in small-scale trading and enterprises; added to these multiple tasks, they spend long hours fetching water and collecting firewood (IFAD, 2021) and regardless of their multiple roles women still contribute to nation's economy and this usually cause a decline in their health (Alade, 2018). Therefore, their multiple role as being domestic, economic and reproductive, emphasizes the need to give attention to women's health condition, especially in rural Nigeria (FAO, 2006).

According to Thiombiano, (2014), women are the backbone of family farming as they account for about half of the agricultural labour force in developing countries; however, low levels of human capital in education, health and nutrition, were constraints on women's labour productivity in agriculture and other sectors, hence the need to create conditions to improve the quality of life associated with family farming, since family farmers and rural women engaged in farming had the right to continue working on what they knew and enjoyed doing and producing in order to sustain agricultural productivity and guarantee food security.

Like their counterparts in most African countries, the bulk of Nigerian women live in the rural areas because fewer than 25% of Nigerians are urban dwellers (Wikipedia, 2021) and HIV/AIDS seems to stand out as the most devastating problem to the economy. Having started in the urban area and now seriously gaining prominence in the rural area that serve as the source of agricultural production. REACH (2010) posited that Nigeria, Africa's most populous country, has the second-highest rate of the disease, with current prevalence estimated at 4.6 percent. An estimated 3 million Nigerians currently live with AIDS, and 280,000 AIDS deaths and 370,000 new infections are reported each year and with Women more biologically, socially and economically vulnerable than men to HIV (FAO, 2017) thus they are more at risk than men, with an estimate of prevalence of 4.4 - 5.9 for young women as against 1.7 - 3.3 for men (UNAIDS, 2000). This could therefore be interpreted to mean that for every man infected with HIV/AIDS, there are three women infected.

Social norms about female sexuality make it very difficult for women and girls around the world to protect themselves from HIV infection. Women and girls are often encouraged to remain uninformed about sexual matters and/or remain sexually passive. In Weiss *et al* (2020), traditional norms of virginity for unmarried girls impede young women's freedom to seek important sexual health information, including knowledge about HIV risk. Women often have limited access to sexual health information and services because of a misguided fear that it will encourage sexual activity. In addition, in order to preserve their virginity, many young women engage in alternative sexual behaviours, such as anal sex, which can increase their risk of acquiring HIV (Gupta, 2000). The expectations for sexual, passivity in women, along with the priority given to male sexual pleasure, also makes it difficult for women to be an equal partner in deciding the terms of sexual activity, including negotiating safer sex practices. The power imbalance between men and women also translates into economic dependency for women. In most societies, men have greater control and access to productive resources.

USAID (2014) attributed the rapid spread of HIV in Nigeria to such factors as sexual networking practices like polygamy, a high prevalence of untreated sexually transmitted disease, low condom use, low literacy, poverty, poor health status of women, which are all very common in rural areas and also stigmatization. The complex mixture of culture, religion and regional political groupings are all challenges to HIV prevention programmes. Despite the various effort put in place to combat this

pandemic in Nigeria especially in Osun state, the prevalence rose from 1.2 percent in 2008 to 2.7 percent in 2010, (FMH- HSS, 2011, O-SACA, 2014) and with a total of 185 men and 280 women affected by the infection in 2004, (SACA, -MOH, Osogbo, 2014), it can be safely concluded that the epidemic in on the rise in Osun state, and that women, more than men are affected. So the research work described the socioeconomic and demographic characteristics of the respondents; identified the information need on household welfare of the respondents; examined the awareness of the respondents of HIV/AIDS prevention strategies; investigated the constraints to utilization of HIV/AIDS prevention strategies by the women in the study area.

Methodology

The study was conducted in the rural areas of Osun State, which is one of the 36 States in Nigeria. It was carved out of the old Oyo state on the 27th of August, 1991 and has its capital as Osogbo. The state is bounded north and south by Kwara and Ogun States and in the east by Ondo and Hkiti States and Oyo state in the west. It lies between longitude 6°51' N and 8° 10'N on the North – Southpole, and longitude 4° 05'and 5° 02' on the East - West pole. The state, which is made up 30 Local Government Areas (LGAs) and one area office covers a vast land area of 8,602 square kilometres is categorized into three agricultural zones, namely: Ife/Ijesa, Osogbo and Iwo. Population distribution as reported by UNFPA(2008) shows that there are 3,416,959 people with 1,734,149 being male, 1,682,810 being female and about 70 percent of this figure residing in rural areas comprising of 19 out of a total of 30 LGAs. Sample and Sampling procedure

Rural women between the ages of 18 and 50 (being the active sexual period for women) years were sampled for the study. Multistage sampling procedure was employed to select the respondents for this study. Three out of thirty local government areas (LGAs) was purposively selected across the three agricultural zones, based on HIV/AIDS prevalence, using-Resident HIV Surveillance report, and from each of the LGAs, three communities were be randomly selected, totaling 9 communities. From all the communities a total of 180 respondents were randomly selected from every other house using proportionate sampling.

Structured interview schedule was used to collect primary data from respondents. Secondary data was obtained from the various agencies that are connected with this work such as Osun state Agricultural Development Programme (OSSADEP), and other agencies working on AIDS such as National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA), Osun state Agency for the Control of AIDS (O-SACA), Local Government Agency for the Control of AIDS, (LACAs) of the concerned local governments, Federal and Osun state ministries of health, and other Non-Governmental Organization (NGOs). Published materials such a books, journals, proceedings, Newspapers, internet and other social media sources relevant to the research work will be consulted to complement the primary data.

The data for this research work was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistics that was used includes frequency count, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Inferential statistics for this study was Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal characteristics of the Respondents

The distribution of the respondent in Table 1 by age revealed that 1.1 percent of the respondents were less than or equal to 20 years, 34.4 percent of the respondent were between the ages of 21 and 30 years while 38.9 percent of the respondents were between 31 and 40 years of age. Also, 22.2 percent of the respondents

were between 41 and 50 years of age. The mean age of the respondent was 34.8 years. This mean age is generally considered to be a youthful age. A little above half (60.6%) of the respondents were married, 12.2 percent of the respondents were single, 15.6 of the respondents were separated while 10.6 percent of the respondents widowed. The distribution of the respondents by household size in revealed that 25% of the respondents had between 1 and 3 household members, 50.5% of the respondents had between 4 and 6, 20.6% of the respondents had more than 10 household members. The mean household size is 5. The distribution of the respondents by the year of schooling revealed that 13.4% of the respondents spent between 1 to 5 years in school, 41.1% of the respondents spent between 6 and 10 years, 42.27 of the respondents spent between 11 and 15 years in school while 3.3% of the respondents spent above 15 years in school. The mean age of schooling is 9.59.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents by Socioeconomic Characteristics

Variable N = 180	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Age			
< 20	2	1.1	34.8
21 – 30	62	34.4	
31 – 40	70	38.9	
41- 50	40	22.2	
>50	6	3.3	
Marital Status			
Single	22	12.2	
Married	109	60.6	
Separated	28	15.6	
Divorce	2	1.1	
Widowed	19	10.5	
Family Type			
Monogamy	99	55	
Polygamy	80	44.4	
Polyandry	1	0.6	
Household Size			
1-3	45	25	4.77
4-6	91	50.5	
7-9	37	20.6	
10 & above	7	3.9	
Religion			
Christianity	78	43.2	
Islam	88	48.9	
Traditional	14	7.8	
Years of Schooling			
1-5	24	13.4	9.59
6-10	74	41.1	
11-15	76	42.2	
16-20	6	3.3	
Membership of Social Organization			
Member	118	65.6	
Non Member	62	34.4	

Frequency of information Needs of the Respondents

The distribution of the respondents by the frequency of information needs as shown in table 2 was measured in a 4-scale of always, often, rarely and never using weighted mean score (WMS). Information need on finance was ranked first with the WMS of 2.76, health was ranked 2nd with the WMS of 1.85 while nutrition was ranked 4th with the WMS of 1.76. Also, information needs on child care and agriculture jointly ranked 5th with the WMS of 0.86. Information needs on family matters ranked 7th with the WMS of 0.49 while information needs on home management ranked 8th with the WMS of 0.42. This is in line with findings of Anugwa and Agwu (2017) that majority of women need information, particularly in the areas of productive resources. Asked why finance and health was topmost on their priorities, most of the respondents argued that these are the two things, without which, one can do nothing and this agrees with the popular saying, ‘health is wealth’

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by the Frequency of Information Need

Type of Information	Always	Often	Rarely	Never	WMS	RANK
Nutrition	31 (17.2)	75 (41.7)	74(41.1)	0	1.76	4 th
Health	76(42.2)	96(42.2)	8(4.4)	0	2.38	2 nd
Child care	19(10.6)	19(10.6)	60(33.3)	82(45.6)	0.86	5 th
Fashion	28(15.6)	101(56.1)	101(56.1)	4(2.2)	1.85	3 rd
Family matters	5(2.8)	17(9.4)	40(22.2)	118(65.6)	0.49	7 th
Finance	138(76.7)	41(22.8)	1(0.6)	0	2.76	1 st
Home Management	12(6.7)	7(3.9)	26(14.4)	135(75.0)	0.42	8 th
Agriculture	4(2.2)	17(9.4)	111(61.7)	48(26.7)	0.86	5 th

Source: field survey, 2023

Awareness/ level of awareness of HIV/ AIDS Preventive strategies.

The distribution of the respondents by their awareness of various HIV preventive strategies revealed in Table 4 that 38.3% of the respondents were aware of abstinence, 68.3% of the respondents were aware of fidelity, while 84.4% of the respondents were aware of condom use. 52.2% of the respondents were aware of voluntary counselling and testing, 25% of the respondents were aware of the need to avoid transmission of untested blood while 85% of the respondents were aware of avoidance of sharing sharp objects.

According to Table 8, the respondents were grouped into levels of awareness of the selected HIV/AIDS prevention strategies by categorization. 47.85, representing the majority fell into the moderate category, while 42.2% fell into high category and 10.0% fell into low category.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Awareness of HIV/AIDS Preventive Strategies

Prevention strategies	Frequency	Percentage
Abstinence	69	38.3
Fidelity	123	68.3
Condom use	152	84.4
Voluntary Counselling and Testing	94	52.2
Avoiding Transmission of Untested Blood	45	25.0
Avoiding Sharing of Sharp Objects	153	85.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Awareness of HIV/AIDS

Results obtained showed in table 3 that 161 respondents, representing 89.4% were aware of the existence of HIV/AIDS while 19 respondents, representing 10.6% were not aware of the HIV/AIDS existence. This is a confirmation to the claim of O’SACA,(2015) that virtually everyone in Osun state is aware of the existence of the deadly HIV/AIDS through her effort of creating awareness among citizens through various means.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents, by categorization into levels of awareness of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies.

Level of Awareness	Frequency	Percentage
High ($\bar{X} \pm 1SD$)	76	42.2
Moderate ($\bar{X} \pm 1SD$)	86	47.8
Low ($\bar{X} \pm 1SD$)	18	10.0
Total	180	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Constraints to the utilization of HIV/AIDS

Constraints to utilization of abstinence as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

The distribution of the respondents according to constraint to utilization of abstinence as a preventive strategy shows in table 5 that 62.8 percent of the respondents recognized stigma as a constraint, 3.3 percent identified unavailability of preventive strategies, 3.9 percent identified cost of accessing strategy as a constraint, 15 percent of the respondents identified complexity of usage as a constraint, 60.6 percent of the respondents identified religious considerations while 62.2 percent of the respondents identified cultural compatibility as the main constraint to the use of abstinence as a preventive strategy. Therefore, stigma (62.8%) and cultural compatibility were the most identified constraints to the use of abstinence as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

Constraints to the use of fidelity as HIV/ AIDS preventive strategy.

The distribution of the respondents in the constraints to the use of fidelity as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy revealed in table 5 that 13.9% identified stigma as the constraint, 2.8 percent identified unavailability as the constraint, 1.1 percent of the respondents identified cost of assessing the strategy as a constraint, 5.6 percent of the respondents identified complexity of usage as the constraint, 7.2 percent identified religious consideration as the constraint while 28.3 percent identified cultural compatibility as the constraint to the usage of fidelity as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy. Therefore, cultural compatibility (28.3) and religion consideration were the most mentioned constraints to the usage of fidelity HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

Constraints to the utilization of Condom as a preventive strategy to HIV/AIDS.

The distribution of the respondents by the utilization of condom as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy as shown in table 14 revealed that 67.8 percent of the respondents identified stigma as the constraint, 54.8 percent identified unavailability of condom as the constraint, 60.6 percent identified cost of assessing condom as the constraint 48.3 percent identified religious consideration as a constraint while 28.3 percent identified cultural compatibility as their constraint to the usage of condom as a preventive strategy. Therefore, stigma (67.8%) and Cost of assessing condom (60.6%) were the most widely mentioned constraints to the use of condom as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

Constraints to the utilization of voluntary counseling and testing as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

The distribution of the respondents by the constraint to the utilization of voluntary counseling and testing as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy revealed in table 5 that 62.8 percent of the respondents identified stigma as the constraint, 63.3 percent identified unavailability of voluntary counseling and testing as the constraint, 56.7 percent of the respondents identified cost of assessing voluntary counseling and testing as the constraint, 38.9 percent of the respondents identified complexity of usage as the constraint, 1.7 percent identified religious considerations as the constraint while 1.1 percent of the respondents identified cultural compatibility as the constraint to the utilization of voluntary counseling and testing as the HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

Constraints to the utilization of avoidance transmission of untested blood as a preventive strategy of HIV/AIDS.

The distribution of the respondents by the constraints to the utilization of avoidance of transmission of untested blood as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy revealed in table 5 that 2.2 percent of the respondents identified stigma as a constraint 58.9 percent of the respondents identified unavailability of avoidance of transmission of untested blood as a preventive strategy, 10 percent identified cost of assessing the strategy as a constraint, 15.6 percent of the respondents identified complexity of usage as a constraint, 3.9 percent of the respondents identified religious consideration as a constraint while 4.4 percent of the respondents identified cultural compatibility as a constraint

Constraints to the utilization of avoidance of sharing sharp objects as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

The distribution of the respondents by the constraints to the utilization of avoidance of sharing sharp objects as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy as shown in table 5 revealed that 36.7 percent of the respondents identified stigma as a constraint, 33.9 percent identified unavailability of the strategy as a constraint, 72.8 percent of the respondents identified cost of assessing the strategy as a constraint, 2.2 percent of the respondents identified complexity of usage as a constraint, 2.2 percent identified religious consideration as the constraint while 7.2 percent identified cultural compatibility as the constraint to the utilization of avoidance of sharing sharp objects as HIV/AIDS preventive strategy.

Table 5: Distribution of the Respondents by Constraints to the Usage of HIV/AIDS Preventive Strategies

Constraints	Stigma	Unavailability	Cost of accessing the strategy	Complexity of usage	Religious consideration	Cultural compatibility
Abstinence	113(62.8)	6(3.3)	7(3.9)	27(15)	108(60.6)	112(62.2)
Fidelity	25(13.9)	5(2.8)	2(1.1)	10(5.6)	13(7.2)	51(28.3)
Condom use	122(67.8)	104(57.8)	109(60.6)	87(48.3)	28(15.6)	37(20.6)
Voluntary counseling and testing	113(62.8)	114(63.3)	102(56.7)	70(38.9)	3(1.7)	2(1.1)
Avoiding transmission of untested blood	4(2.2)	106(58.9)	18(10.0)	28(15.6)	7(3.9)	8(4.4)
Avoiding sharing of sharp objects	66(36.7)	61(33.9)	131(72.8)	4(2.2)	4(2.2)	13(7.2)

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Hypothesis

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between some selected socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies. The results of Pearson Product Moment Correlation in table 6 showing relationship between some selected socioeconomic characteristics of the respondents and the utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies revealed that a significant relationships exist between age ($r = 0.219^{**}$ $p = 0.003$) of the respondents, years of schooling ($r = 0.606^{**}$, $p = 0.000$), farming experience ($r = 0.488^{**}$ $p = 0.000$) and the years of staying in the community ($r = 0.326^{**}$ $p = 0.000$) and utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies.

Table 6: Correlation analysis showing the relationship between some selected socio-demographic characteristics and utilization of HIV/AIDS prevention strategies

Socioeconomic Characteristics	R value	P value	Remarks
Age	0.219 ^{**}	0.003	Significant
Household Size	0.055	0.464	Not Significant
Years of schooling	0.606 ^{**}	0.000	Significant
Farming Experience	0.488 ^{**}	0.000	Significant
Years of staying in the Community	0.326 ^{**}	0.000	Significant

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Conclusion

The respondents were in their active and productive age with relatively large household size. All the major HIV/AIDS preventive strategies were available to the respondents with Condom being the most utilized of all the preventive strategies. The major constraints to the utilization of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies were stigmatization and cost of assessing the preventive strategies. It's therefore recommended that more awareness needs to be done against stigmatization of the usage of various preventive strategies and Condom should be made readily available to the respondents in order to curb the menace of HIV/AIDS.

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